

A DISTRIBUTED TELECOMMUNICATION NETWORK MONITORING SYSTEM MODEL

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Abstract

This article analyzes models of distributed optical telecommunications network monitoring systems built using a multi-level architecture. This architecture encompasses system management, testing, and the collection of statistical data on signal propagation during ordinary, extraordinary, or emergency situations, as well as system management and administration. Implementing monitoring tasks within a multi-level architecture—that is, at the physical, logical, informational, and administrative levels—requires developing a mathematical model of the distributed optical telecommunications network monitoring system itself. This article therefore analyzes the construction of a distributed monitoring system model, a mathematical operating model using leakage theory, and a dynamic reliability model. A four-level model of distributed optical telecommunications network monitoring systems has been developed, enabling fundamental constraints on reliability characteristics to be derived based on the critical probability, the value of which is determined by the design principles of the overall distributed optical telecommunications network monitoring system.

Keywords: monitoring system model, monitoring subsystem, optical linear path, optical telecommunication network, multi-level architecture, unauthorized entry.

Introduction. The distributed monitoring system model is a multi-level architecture that enables detection of unauthorized intrusion into the optical linear path of a telecommunications network, processing of data received from sensors, and making appropriate decisions. The functioning of an optical telecommunications network is impossible without monitoring at various levels. In this case, the monitoring process is reduced to automatic, semi-automatic, or manual monitoring, its testing, and collection of statistical data on the state of the optical telecommunications network linear path in the event of unauthorized intrusions and various emergency situations, as well as monitoring or administrative management of the optical telecommunications network. In turn, these functions cannot be implemented without various types of signaling about the state of the optical telecommunications network via special built-in or reserved optical channels connecting the monitoring subsystems and the managed systems or network elements [1,10]. To implement monitoring tasks at the physical, logical, informational and administrative levels, of which the last two belong to a special

category of monitoring, it is necessary to develop a multi-level architecture of a model of a distributed monitoring system for an optical telecommunications network and describe the connections necessary for implementing monitoring functions in various sections of this network.

Development of a distributed monitoring system model. Unlike existing optical telecommunication systems with PDH (plesiochronous digital hierarchy), which lack a standard description of the model and interfaces and dedicated control communication channels, systems with SDH (synchronous digital hierarchy) have their own control systems based on a well-developed system of standards describing the models, interfaces, interaction scheme of functional blocks and control channels. In this regard, the functional model of a distributed monitoring system can be represented by a 4-level model [1], where each level performs a specific function, presenting to the upper level a picture of the functioning of the optical telecommunication network, successively generalized by the lower levels (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Model of a distributed telecommunications network monitoring system

The top level of the distributed optical telecommunications network monitoring system model consists of the distributed monitoring system, the second level consists of monitoring subsystems, the third level consists of the optical signal transmission monitoring network, and the fourth level consists of the monitoring of the entire optical telecommunications network. In this case, optimal implementation of the distributed monitoring system model for managing the operation, administration, and maintenance of the switching system (SS) and optical telecommunications system (OTS) of the SDH/SONET synchronous digital network is a pressing research objective. Therefore, the process of monitoring and maintaining the optical line path at the physical layer is closely linked to the development of a four-level model of the distributed monitoring and control system for the SDH/SONET synchronous telecommunications network, including its individual components.

Mathematical model of a distributed monitoring and control system. The management of a distributed monitoring system consists of the operation, administration, and maintenance of a synchronous SDH/SONET network and can be divided into the following levels [5]:

- business management, i.e., the top-level management of the economic and practical efficiency of the network;
- service management, i.e., the level of network service management;
- network management, i.e., the level of network management systems;
- element management, i.e., the lower level of element managers or systems for managing network elements.

Let's assume that each network element is operational with probability P , and the links between them are operational with probability R . In the monitoring subsystem, we identify a maximum cluster of network elements with a size of $n = n_1^2$. The operation of network elements can be viewed as the transmission of a monitoring signal (data and commands) through operational monitoring subsystems and the links between them. Monitoring subsystems are considered operational if such transmission is possible, and, in addition, the operational part forms a connected cluster (from the set of monitoring subsystems) containing $n_c \geq n_0$ control modules, where n_0 – is the minimum number of monitoring subsystems required to select and represent a specific optical monitoring channel.

Increasing the redundancy of the monitoring subsystem is an increase in size n and at $n \rightarrow \infty$ the monitoring subsystem must have an infinite healthy cluster.

Otherwise, the monitoring subsystem splits into disconnected parts and will not be able to function with any number of healthy monitoring subsystems. The question then arises: at what probabilities P and R does the monitoring subsystem have an infinite healthy cluster?

The answer to the question posed is the main content of the leakage theory [8,9]. Let us dwell on the problem of leakage through the monitoring subsystem, when $P < 1$, and $R = 1$. Leakage through connections ($P = 1, R < 1$) is reduced to leakage through the monitoring subsystem, so that everywhere below the term “monitoring subsystem” can be replaced by the term “connection”, and the symbol P by the symbol R . Therefore, it is necessary to conduct a study of the structural reliability of the monitoring subsystem, considering the connections between the monitoring subsystems to be absolutely reliable.

In relation to the problem at hand, the result of the seepage theory that we need can be formulated as follows [8].

Statement 1. For any periodic control graph G of the optical channel monitoring and maintenance process mapped to a set of monitoring subsystem N^2 , there exists a critical probability P_k such that if $P < P_k$, then an infinite healthy cluster of the monitoring subsystem exists in G with probability 0, and if $P \geq P_k$, then there exists a unique infinite healthy cluster G in with probability 1.

Let $P(n, p)$ – be the probability of a monitoring signal leaking through a healthy cluster of the monitoring subsystem G with size $n = n_1^2$ at a given time. This value is called the availability coefficient of the monitoring subsystem. Then the following statement is obvious.

Statement 2. On the set of healthy clusters of local control systems of the same type mapped to K^2 ,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P(n, p) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } P < P_k, \\ 1 & \text{for } P \geq P_k. \end{cases}$$

In other words, with increasing redundancy, the control system becomes arbitrarily reliable if $P \geq P_k$, and arbitrarily unreliable if $P < P_k$.

$$P(t + \Delta t) = P(t) - \alpha \cdot P(t)\Delta t + \beta [1 - P(t)]\Delta t,$$

Figure $P(n, p)$ clearly demonstrates the typical behavior of Fig. 2. It is evident that with increasing n , function $P(n, p)$ tends to become stepwise, and, in addition, the inflection point $P(n, p)$ tends to the leakage threshold P_k .

Fig. 2. Dependence of the probability of leakage through a healthy cluster of the monitoring subsystem on the probability of each healthy network element

Thus, in the interval (0,1), the root of equation $P_p^n(n, p) = 0$ is an estimate of the leakage threshold, which is already quite acceptable at $n = 16$. In this case, the problem of obtaining the coefficients of polynomial $P(n, p)$ has a time complexity of $T(n) \geq O(2^n)$, which provides a limitation on the further complication of the problem.

Dynamic model of operational reliability of the monitoring subsystem. The analysis of the structural reliability of the monitoring subsystem in dynamics is clear from statement 1. We will consider an ensemble of independent and identical elements of the monitoring subsystem and require the condition to be satisfied everywhere.

$$P \geq P_k. \quad (1)$$

Let the failure-free operation time of the monitoring subsystem be distributed according to an exponential law with parameter and the mean time between failures for such a monitoring subsystem be equal to $\tau = \alpha^{-1}$. The quantity α is the failure rate of the mon-

itoring subsystem, and τ is the lifetime of the element. A failed module is detected and restored with an intensity of β , and the mean recovery time is β^{-1} . Now, for the probability P of the serviceable state of the monitoring subsystem at time $t + \Delta t$ we can write from here, with $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$ we have

$$dP(t) = \{\beta \cdot [1 - P(t)] - \alpha \cdot P(t)\} dt \quad (2)$$

Let $P_0(t) = P(0)$ and $P = P(t)$. Probability P_0 characterizes the failure of the monitoring subsystem and if the faulty elements can be restored, then $P_0 = 1$. The solution to equation (1) under the specified initial conditions has the form:

$$P = P_\infty + (P_0 - P_\infty)e^{-(\alpha + \beta)t}, \quad (3)$$

where $P_\infty = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} P = \beta / (\alpha + \beta)$ is the final probability of the monitoring subsystem being in good working order.

Equation (3) describes the process of death-recovery of the set of the monitoring subsystem, which is presented in Fig. 3.

Fig. 5. Diagram of the process of destruction and restoration of multiple elements of the monitoring subsystem

Considering requirement (1) as a condition for the connectivity of the monitoring subsystem elements, the following statement can be formulated.

Statement 3. The lifetime of an infinite healthy cluster in the local set of the monitoring subsystem is:

$$t = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{for } P_0 < P_\infty < P_k, \\ \frac{1}{\alpha + \beta} \cdot \ln \frac{P_0 - P_\infty}{P_k - P_\infty}, & \text{for } P_\infty < P_k < P_0, \\ \infty, & \text{for } P_k < P_\infty. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

In particular, in a system without recovery at $\beta = 0$

$$t = \tau \cdot \ln \frac{P_0}{P_k} \leq -\tau \cdot \ln P_k, \quad (5)$$

where $\tau = \alpha^{-1}$ – is the lifetime of one element of the monitoring subsystem set.

So, a monitoring subsystem with an infinite number of monitoring subsystem elements can function indefinitely if $\beta / (\alpha + \beta) \geq P_k$. Otherwise, redundancy does not increase the monitoring subsystem's operating time.

However, redundancy must be guaranteed not only by the health of the monitoring subsystem set, but also by the presence of the monitoring subsystem in a healthy cluster $n_k > n_0$. In a finite set containing a sufficiently large number of monitoring subsystem elements, the size of the healthy set is $n_k = n \cdot P_p$, where P_p – is the probability of a particular monitoring subsystem element being in a healthy cluster.

From here $n \geq n_0 \cdot P_p^{-1}$.

It is clear that $P_p(P_k) < P_k$, where

$$n \geq n_0 \cdot P_p^{-1}. \quad (6)$$

A suspicion arises that, given the high redundancy of the monitoring subsystem, it will fail before the critical number of monitoring subsystem elements in a healthy cluster is reached.

Let's consider monitoring subsystem elements with limited recovery. Further, it's sufficient to use the approximate method of average dynamics and consider only the steady state. Let n – be the number of monitoring subsystem elements, m – the number of recovery units, α and β – the failure and recovery rates, respectively.

For $m > n(1-P)$, the monitoring subsystem behaves as self-healing, while for $m < n(1-P)$ limited recovery occurs, and the condition for equality of failure and recovery rates is as follows:

$$n \cdot \alpha \cdot P = m \cdot \beta. \quad (7)$$

It is also known that when a limited recovery system is fully loaded, the mathematical expectation of the number of serviceable elements of the monitoring subsystem is $m\beta\alpha^{-1}$. We require that this number exceed n_0 and, in addition, that $P > P_k$ be satisfied.

Taking into account (7), we have.

Statement 4. A monitoring subsystem with limited recovery is operational if condition $n_0 < m \cdot \beta \cdot \alpha^{-1} \leq n \leq m \cdot \beta (\alpha \cdot P_k)^{-1}$ is met. Otherwise, if condition $n > m \cdot \beta (\alpha \cdot P_k)^{-1}$ or $m\beta\alpha^{-1} < n_0$ is met, the system's steady state is a failure state.

These results suggest that, for practical applications, it is important to maintain not only a healthy cluster but also a similar structure for which optical channel monitoring algorithms have been developed.

In [3,5], specific reconfiguration algorithms for a faulty structure are considered, ensuring the restoration

of the original matrix of size n_1^2 . This is achieved by placing a spare column and row on the matrix. Preservation of the structure is possible if the number of failures is of the order of n_1 . Taking the value $(n - n_1) \cdot n^{-1}$ as an estimate of the probability of P_k , we have $\lim P_k = 1$ for $n \rightarrow \infty$. Increasing the matrix size decreases its lifetime. Apparently, the reserve should be distributed uniformly throughout the structure, and its reconfiguration should not disrupt the operation of the entire optical telecommunication system. Global reconfiguration is equivalent to a limitation on the number of restoring devices of $m = 1$, which is undesirable by virtue of assertion 4.

Conclusion.

Thus, the developed four-level model of a distributed SDH/SONET network monitoring and control system allows us to derive fundamental constraints on reliability characteristics based on the critical probability, the value of which is determined by the design principles of the monitoring subsystem for optical information transmission systems.

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